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CIP

COWAM in Practice

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First annual activity summary
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Dissemination level

PU	Public	PU
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the partners of the CIP project	
CO	Confidential, only for partners of the CIP project	

The objectives of COWAM in Practice (CIP) are:

- to contribute to **enabling European societies to make actual progress** in the governance of **radioactive waste management (RWM)** while contributing to **increasing societal awareness of and accountability for radioactive waste management in Europe** in order to reach practicable, accountable and sustainable decisions
- to **follow up and analyse five innovative national processes** on RWM on the basis of **COWAM-2 results** with a view to **support stakeholders, particularly local communities, directly in their engagement** with their particular RWM programme(s) – and to capture the learning from that experience
- to develop **best practices and guidance for the application** (implementation and improvement) of **new inclusive governance of RWM approaches in the EU-25**, including benchmarking on practicable and sustainable decision making processes recognised as fair and equitable by the stakeholders on the short, medium and long term.

These objectives are achieved through the live and direct assessment by concerned stakeholders¹ of ongoing processes in five Member States (France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and UK) through two main interrelated activities:

- For each country a **national stakeholder group (NSG) review, from a local perspective, the inclusive governance approaches developed in their country**, and elaborate a **prospective case study**.
- Based on the national reviews, a **team of experts** will draw lessons and bring out **EU-level guidelines** for inclusive governance of RWM.

Particular objectives for the first year were:

- To set up the national stakeholder group (NSG) in France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom.
- To develop a common understanding, among CIP members (including NSG chairs), of
 - the RWM governance situations in the five countries
 - the common methodological framework at European level
 - research results from COWAM-2 project
 - possible investigations proposed in CIP
- To prepare background material on these aspects for presentation in the first NSG meetings
- To prepare and manage the first NSG meetings, with a view to identifying the research investigations requested by NSG
- To make first proposals to address these requests
 - providing a thematic structure

¹ Throughout, the term “stakeholders” refers to all those with a role or interest in the RWM process.

- identifying possible case studies or other research material (existing or to be developed)

During the first year of the project national stakeholder groups were indeed established in the five countries involved in CIP, namely France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom. In parallel, the frame for the research investigations was elaborated in interaction between the NSG and the methodological task force (hereafter MTF).

Thus the project developed in four main phases.

- Phase 1 – Inception of national stakeholder groups (January-February 2007)
- Phase 2 – Kick-off and core group meetings (March-May 2007)
- Phase 3 – First national stakeholder group meetings (June-July 2007)
- Phase 4 – Second core group meeting and preparation of the second NSG meetings (September-December 2007).

In most phases, the activities of WP1 (National Facilitators) and WP2 (Methodological Task Force) were very much intertwined. WP1 deals with the inception and facilitation of NSG, while WP2 takes care of the research investigations. Since the project is a cooperative research, there are constantly interactions between the national facilitators and the MTF as well as with the management board (coordinator and WP leaders).

A summary of each phase is given below.

Phase 1 – Inception of national stakeholder groups (January-February 2007)

CIP is based on cooperation between research teams and stakeholders. The project relies on both the resources and skills of the “consortium participants” on the one hand and the involvement of a large network of stakeholders in RWM on the other hand in the five countries involved. The cooperative research implies establishment of a pluralistic group of stakeholders in each of the five countries.

The *principle* of the groups was discussed in each country before the project started with the major stakeholders. The project started with an inception phase to set up *practically* these groups with the following goals:

- developing a common understanding of the project’s objectives and process among stakeholders in each country
- adapting the project’s orientations to stakeholders’ expectations and situation in each country
- providing “NSG guidelines” and a structured dialogue methodology for group discussions.

During this inception phase, the need was felt for close interactions between national facilitators and the WP leaders in order to share information about latest development in the five countries, to develop a stronger mutual understanding of the context where CIP is to build on, and to prepare and refine the practical implementation of the cooperative methodology in this context. This need was met through intensive e-mail correspondence, as well as (additional) meetings (travel by one or two management board members to each context).

Phase 2 – Kick-off and core group meetings (March-May 2007)

The kick-off meeting of the project (7-8 March 2007), with all contractors and steering committee (SC) members, established the background, objectives, rules and schedule for the project.

Importantly, it was a first opportunity to share information among partners and advisory participants about the situation of the five countries as regards RWM governance, and to identify topical issues.

During the kick-off meeting, the steering committee held its first meeting together with National Facilitators and established success criteria for the project to orient and follow the project implementation. The steering committee will meet once every year.

In parallel to the steering committee meeting, the methodological task force held its own session and started to structure the research themes and organise its work.

These discussions were carried on in a core group meeting on 4 May 2007. The main purpose of the discussions was to share COWAM-2 results, and provide background material for the first NSG meetings:

- a presentation and a synthesis of COWAM-2 results
- proposals for CIP investigations
- NSG guidelines comprising a “cooperation framework” with rules of cooperation and rules of procedure, and a “common agenda for the first NSG meeting”.

Phase 3 – First national stakeholder group meetings (June-July 2007)

This first round of NSG meetings was the achievement of the networking efforts made by the National Facilitators in the first six months to set up a group of stakeholders in radwaste governance in their country. Setting a good basis for three years of cooperation, this first round was of key importance also to elaborate the research demand from each country. The first meetings of the NSG were held at the following dates and places:

- Romania: 1 June 2007, Cernavoda
- France: 28 June 2007, Paris
- Slovenia: 20 June 2007, Krsko
- Spain: 5 July 2007, Madrid
- United Kingdom: 19 July 2007, Manchester.

Phase 4 – Second core group meeting and preparation of the second NSG meetings (September-December 2007)

Following the first NSG meetings and the discussion of the CIP work programme in the NSG in June-July 2007, the management board gathered and analysed the research requests of the five countries in September 2007.

It resulted in the research structure being reframed along three main themes of investigations:

- Theme 1: Affected communities and sustainable territorial development programmes
- Theme 2: Structuring local communities and development of participative democracy in radioactive waste management governance
- Theme 3: Long-term issues for a sustainable governance of radioactive waste.

To meet the individual NSG requests, the methodological task force identified and prepared case studies and other research material to be presented and discussed in the second NSG meeting.